

Profile of Critical Thinking Skills on Fluid Mechanics Material by Senior High School Students in Makassar City

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 27, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: January 16, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords Descriptive, Fluid Mechanics, Profile, Students' Critical Thinking Skills</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4445157</p>	<p><i>This study aims to analyze the profile of students' critical thinking skills on Fluid Mechanics material based on the indicators of interpretation, analysis, and evaluation. Measurement was carried out on 714 students at 5 senior high schools in Makassar City. This research was conducted on August – October 2020. The results showed that the critical thinking skills of senior high school students in Makassar City are relatively weak as indicated by an average percentage above 50.0% on all indicators. All students demonstrated relatively consistent critical thinking skill performance on each item for each indicator. Most students with strong critical thinking skills are from the same school and so do the students with weak critical thinking skills. It indicates that it is most likely the learning model applied by teachers affects the students' critical thinking skills, particularly on Fluid Mechanics material.</i></p>

Introduction

The 21st Century life skills require a wide range of skills. At least 7 life skills are needed on job life, including critical thinking and problem solving skills, collaboration and leadership skills, agility and adaptability, as well as initiative and entrepreneur spirit (Andi, K., &Arafah, B. 2017). Other skills include communication skills, accessing and analyzing information, and curiousness and imagination (Wagner, 2010). So education, ICT, innovation and science technology are the main pillars of knowledge society (Malik, 2018).

Teachers must also comprehend the skills stated above and realize that they are required to be able to compete in future. In teaching, teachers should continuously strive to train their students' critical thinking skills or CTS (Arafah, B. &Kaharuddin 2019). Students with good critical thinking skills will perform better academically at school (Arafah, K., Rusyadi, R., Arafah, B., &Arafah, A. N. B. 2020). In addition, they will also be better prepared to face the harsh competition and increase academic expectations in universities (Changwong, Sukkamart, and Sisan, 2018, Arafah, B. &Hasyim, M. 2019). Scientific Critical Thinking (SCT) model is one of the learning models that can improve students' critical thinking and self efficacy skills (Rusmansyah, Leny, Y., Muslimin, I., Isnawati, 2018). While self efficacy directly affects students' motivation of outstanding (Arafah, et. al, 2020).

Students with strong CTS tend to have better problem solving skills (Arafah, A. N. B., &Setiyawati, D. 2020). Meanwhile, the life problems the students may face in future would also continue to be more complex. It indicates that the students must prepare themselves with better CTS to solve various kinds of life problems in the future. Therefore, Indonesian government is required to have comprehensive mapping of student CTS. Currently, there is no a map on student CTS in Makassar city. This research is therefore providing answers about the unavailability of data on student' CTS of physics.

Literature Review

Critical thinking is a skill needed to be able to think critically on a wide range of issues. Those skills include observation, analysis, interpretation, reflection, evaluation, inference, explanation, problem solving, and decision making (Arafah, B., &Kaharuddin, (2019). In particular we must be able to think about a topic or problem objectively and critically.

With respect to the critical thinking, Orlich, et al (2010) stated that ability associated with the effective critical thinking includes observing and identifying patterns, relationships, assumption of logical and reason errors. It's also about building, classifying, comparing and distinguishing criteria. Another important thing is how to interpret, summarize, analyze, synthesize, generalize and hypothesize, and distinguish data.

Ennis (1962) argued that construing critical thinking as "the correct assessment of statements," 12 overlapping characteristics of the critical thinker were presented along with appropriate lists of criteria. A logical analysis of the 12 abilities is made along 3 dimensions: logical, critical, and pragmatic. These three dimensions should be continuously trained develop the logical and critical thinking in decision making. These critical thinking skills are oriented to problem solving both in school environment, world of work, and daily life. Ennis (2011) completed his definition of critical thinking skills as a reflective thinking skill to focus on what to believe and to do when confronting a problem.

Facione (2013) divides the Critical thinking skill (CTS) indicators into interpretation, analysis, evaluation, conclusion, explanation, and self-regulation. Interpretation refers to understand and express the meaning or significance of various experiences, situations, data, events, assessments, conventions, beliefs, procedures, or criteria (Kaharuddin, Ahmad, D, Mardiana, Rusni 2020). The analysis is to identify the desired and actual inferential relationship between statements, questions, concepts, descriptions, or other forms of representation intended to express beliefs, judgments, experiences, reasons, information, or opinions (Kaharuddin, Hikmawati, Arafah, B. 2019). The evaluation is to assess the credibility of a statement or other representations as a record or description of a person's perception, experience, situation, judgment, belief, or opinion (Arafah, B., Thayyib, M., Kaharuddin, & Sahib, H. 2020). In addition, the evaluation has a sense of assessing the logical strength of actual or desired inferential relationship between statements, descriptions, questions, or other forms of representation (Facione, 2013, Arafah, H. B., & Bahar, A. K. 2015). This study examined only 3 indicators: interpretation, analysis, and evaluation.

Method

This research is a descriptive quantitative research. Data collection was conducted through a survey of 714 students. This research was conducted from August to October 2020 at 5 five state-senior high schools (SMAN) in Makassar City: SMAN 2 Makassar, SMAN 4 Makassar, SMAN 8 Makassar, SMAN 9 Makassar, and SMAN 22 Makassar. CTS data were collected by standardized instruments of researcher.

Content validity was analyzed using Gregory equation (2015) and obtained a consistency between raters of 0.92. The instrument was empirically tested to 100 students, and obtained 40 valid items with a reliability 0.87. The validity was calculated by biserial point equation (Brown, 1988), and the reliability by KR-20 (Kuder & Richardson, 1937).

The data is presented in table to determine the strong, inter-border, and weak categories for each CTS indicator being studied. This categorization is intended to describe the data about CTS profiles of senior high school students in Makassar City. To create a graphic, the data is processed by using the Microsoft Excel 2010 program.

Results and Discussion

The CTS data of senior high school students in Makassar City are presented in three large sections: 1) a description based on the category of each indicator, 2) graphic of respondents' characteristics in each indicator, and 3) graphic of total CTS of students. The following are presented one by one the CTS of senior high school students in Makassar City. Figure-1 shows the category of each CTS indicator in Facione's opinion (2013). The interpretation indicator shows that most students have CTS characteristic (64.3%) of weak category. Followed by the inter-border category (19.5%) and the strong category (16.2%). If the percentage of inter-border categories and strong categories is summed up, then the figure will be 35.7%. This number is quite high when viewed from the point of Covid-19 pandemic, because the teaching is not considered maximal. It means that the CTS of senior high school students (SMAN) in Makassar city is still monitored even though the teacher's learning is not maximal.

Figure-1. Students' CTS categories based on indicators in SMAN in Makassar City

The indicator *Analysis* of CTS show that 54.9% students are still in weak category. However, this result is still lower when compared to the indicator *interpretation*. It means that the students have higher CTS ability in Fluid Mechanics material in indicator *analysis* than in the indicator *interpretation*. Figure-1 also shows that for the indicator *analysis* with a percentage of 27.3% is in the inter-border category. This percentage increases in number when compared to the indicator *interpretation*. Meanwhile, for the indicator *analysis* in weak category (17.8%) increases slightly when compared to indicator *interpretation*.

In indicator *evaluation*, the vast majority of students (68.5%) still have weak CTS. There are 15.1% students having CTS in inter-border category. Similarly, there are 16.4% students with weak CTS. Based on this data, it can be said that the largest percentage is in the indicator *evaluation* when compared to the previous two indicators. It means that of the three indicators studied in this research, it appears that most students do not yet have CTS on the indicator *evaluation*. The result of this study is in accordance with the research by Utami, et al (2018) in Karanganyar, Central Java of Indonesia.

The CTS profile of each respondent in each indicator is presented in figure-2.

Figure-2. CTS profile of SMAN students in each indicator in Makassar City

Most respondents (students) have weak CTS. However, some students still have strong CTS. Interestingly, students' CTS characteristic, both in interpretation, analysis, and evaluation indicators, is relatively consistent. The scores of respondents 209,220,234,256, 441, 470, 623, and 713 consistently showed performance on each CTS indicator. Respondents with weak CTS in indicator *interpretation* also tend to be weak on indicators *analysis* and *evaluation*. Similarly, other respondents also show relatively similar performance in indicators *evaluation*, *analysis* and *evaluation*.

Total scores of CTS of each student in SMAN in Makassar City are presented in figure-3

Figure-3. Total score of CTS of each students in SMAN Makassar City

Figure-3 above shows that the spread of CTS scores of the state-high school (SMAN) students in Makassar City is in general still weak, although some are strong. Static Fluids and Dynamic Fluids materials are thought to require special learning models to train the students' CTS. If traced it further, it was found that the respondents with strong CTS are from the same school. Likewise the students with inter-border and weak CTS are also from

the same school. These CTS differences are thought to be the result of differences in learning models used by teachers. It is suspected that most likely the teachers apply different learning models. In addition, the difference in students' CTS may also be due to the differences of students' characteristics.

Students with strong CTS in Fluid Mechanics material were taught using problem based learning (PBL) model. The PBL learning model helps students to improve thinking skills and problem-solving skills, learn adult roles and become independent learners (Arends, 2012, Floriani, R., Arafah, B., &Arafah, A. N. B. 2020). The critical thinking skills of the students of SMAN 4 Singaraja on which the PBL model was applied have also been proven by Lisniandila, Santyasa, and Suswandi (2018). Likewise Kamil, Velina, and Kamelia (2019) recommended the application of PBL to improve students' CTS. The application of PBL can help students to develop critical thinking skills. Critical thinking ability needs to be developed by students as an effort to prepare themselves to confront the challenges and problems that will be encountered now and later (Fakhriyah, 2014). Meanwhile, students with weak CTS are generally taught using direct instruction by their teachers. Some other teachers apply cooperative learning models, but this model is not maximal because of the covid-19 pandemic. Interaction between students as required in the syntax of cooperative learning model becomes not maximal.

Conclusion

Based on the findings and data analysis of this research, the conclusion is that the overall profile of critical thinking skills of state-high school (SMAN) students in Makassar City is still relatively weak. It tends to be consistent on every item for all indicators measured. The students tend to have the weakest critical thinking skills on the indicator *interpretation*.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, it is recommended to physics teachers to practice in their teaching the students' ability in making interpretation. In addition, further research is also recommended on the use of learning models by which students' critical thinking skills can be built.

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